

Influence of Pesticides on the Trace Element Status of Soils: Part I (Nemagon and BHC on Boron, Cobalt and Copper).

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The results of pesticide application on the soil biochemistry of boron, copper and cobalt in a saline sodic soil have been examined. The results revealed an optimum effect on the trace elements with 0.3 ml of nemagon or B.H.C. per Kg of soil at an interval of 30 days of application. The trace element status then declined. The results have been explained on the basis of chemical and microbial activity in soil.

THE ever growing importance of the use of pesticides in crop production arouses interest from the standpoint of their accumulation in soils and their effects on soil properties. While this subject has been studied in considerable detail by several workers¹⁻⁶, information on the influence of pesticides on the trace element status of soil is lacking. Since trace elements like boron, cobalt and copper play an important role in plant metabolism and animal nutrition or toxicity, it was considered that a study of the effects of 1,2-dibromo-3-chloropropane, commonly known as nemagon and benzene hexachloride (B.H.C.) on the availability of the above elements in soil will be of considerable interest. The soil selected for these investigations was of a sodic saline nature from the district of Aligarh in Uttar Pradesh.

Experimental

The physico-chemical properties of the soil (depth 0-30 cm) used for study were determined and were as follows: $pH = 8.8$, $E.C. = 4.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mho cm}^{-1}$, organic matter = 0.41%, water soluble boron, available copper, total copper and total cobalt being 2.10, 1.12, 41.50 and 15.50 ppm respectively.

The experiments on the influence of pesticides on the trace elements were done in earthenware pots of 20×20 cm size lined with polythene sheets to prevent absorption of water. The plots containing one kilogram soil in each case were treated to water holding capacity with distilled water. Six doses of nemagon (0.0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4 and 0.5 ml) were then injected to a depth of 12 cm in two replications without growing any crop. The plots were maintained to water holding capacity throughout the course of the experiment. The treated samples were periodically drawn by a soil sampler at intervals of 15 days and then analysed for water soluble boron, available and total copper and total cobalt.

The pH and electrical conductivity were measured in 1:5 soil water suspension at $25^\circ \pm 1^\circ$. Organic

matter was estimated as per Walkley and Black's method⁷ using potassium dichromate, sulphuric acid and ferrous ammonium sulphate as reagents. Water soluble boron extracted as per Berger and Troug⁸ was estimated with curcumin oxalic acid reagent as per Dible, *et al.*⁹ with absorbance recorded at 540 nm with Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 20. Total cobalt was estimated colorimetrically using perchloric acid as extractant and 2-nitroso- β -naphthol, as colour reagent¹⁰ at 530 nm. Cheng and Bray's improved carbamate¹¹ procedure was followed to estimate total and available copper; total copper having been extracted *vide* perchloric acid digestion process and available copper *vide* neutral ammonium acetate extraction¹² with absorbance recorded at 440 nm. Blanks were used in all cases.

Results

The average of replicated values are recorded in Table 1.

The data were subjected to statistical analysis of variance according to the two way classification with one observation per cell, the null hypothesis being the equality of the effects of different doses and different time intervals. Correlation coefficients were also calculated. The results are given in Table 1. The effects of B.H.C. were similar and for the sake of brevity are not given here.

Discussion

An examination of the influence of the pesticide mentioned above (Table 1), showed that as compared to the control, water soluble boron significantly increased, reached a maximum value with 0.3 ml dose at 30 days of its application and then declined. The influence followed the dose order $0.3 > 0.2 > 0.4 > 0.1 > 0.5 > 0.0$ ml nemagon per kg soil. The mechanism by which an increase occurred in the water soluble boron has been variously reported by Berger.¹³ The increase in water soluble boron

TABLE 1

EFFECT OF NEMAGON ON THE MICRONUTRIENT AVAILABILITY FOR DIFFERENT DOSES OF THE INSECTICIDE AT VARIOUS INTERVALS OF TIME

Applications : Doses 'in ml per Kg of soil/ days	Average values of micronutrients for various doses and days in ppm					
	Available Cu	Total Cu	Water soluble B	Total Co	pH	Ec. $\times 10^{-4}$ mhos cm^{-1}
0.0	1.35	42.43	2.32	16.43	8.55	3.97
0.1	1.48	42.89	2.45	16.77	8.53	3.90
0.2	1.56	43.18	2.51	16.82	8.59	3.81
0.3	1.68	43.58	2.68	17.01	8.59	3.80
0.4	1.50	43.38	2.48	16.99	8.58	3.73
0.5	1.41	43.59	2.40	16.99	8.58	3.77
LSD	0.013	0.233	0.013	0.346	0.049	0.299
Variance ratio	20.466	11.792	26.510	1.200	0.756	1.845
0 days	1.10	41.47	2.10	15.47	8.32	3.00
15 days	1.54	42.57	2.62	17.11	8.51	4.31
30 days	1.91	45.07	2.96	17.90	8.62	4.32
45 days	1.77	44.33	2.72	17.53	8.54	3.67
60 days	1.58	43.49	2.40	16.89	8.54	4.29
75 days	1.35	42.96	2.35	16.66	8.71	3.61
90 days	1.23	42.66	2.17	16.25	8.74	3.63
LSD	0.012	0.212	0.012	0.316	0.044	0.327
Variance ratio	116.280	64.000	134.890	8.533	17.460	0.211

with a peak at 0.3 ml dose and 30 days of application appeared to be due to its liberation from organic matter in a mineralised form by the stimulated activity of fumigant resistant bacteria which led to decomposition of organic matter as the soil was wetted with water. The results found support from the work of Wensley¹⁴ and Martin *et al.*¹⁵ who have reported an enhanced microbial activity in soils as a result of fumigation. The thiobacilli bacteria seemed to have played a notable part in the solubilisation of boron. The decline with passage of time appeared to be due to the dissipation of the chemical with re-establishment of boron fixing bacteria and adsorption of boron by soil minerals.

The influence of nemagon on available and total copper both with doses and passage of time is represented by the results (vide Table 1).

An examination of the data in Table 1 revealed that available copper increased significantly in soil with fumigation reaching a maximum at 0.3 ml of fumigant per kg soil at 30 days after application. Total copper was similarly affected with the difference that the effect became steady at 0.3 ml dose with no further increase or decrease with increase in dosage.

An increase in total copper in the soil was derived from the toxic effect of the chemical on certain microorganisms. As these organisms were killed by the fumigant, their protoplasmic constituent such as cytochrome oxidase¹⁶ came into the soil leading to an increase in copper. With passage of time (> 30 days) the effect of the chemical declined and the fumigant sensitive microorganism re-established themselves leading to a decrease in copper. On the other hand increase in available copper was due to solubilization effects caused by soil fungi such as *Aspergillus niger*¹⁷ and certain bacteria such as *Thiobacillus*. The negative influence on copper was due to reduction in biological activity by high doses of the fumigant (> 0.3 ml per kg soil) and due to adsorption of available copper by soil minerals with passage of time.

A reference to Table 1 further revealed that total cobalt increased nonsignificantly in the soil as a result of fumigation and significantly with passage of time upto 30 days. The effect of dose order was $0.5 = 0.4 = 0.3 > 0.2 > 0.1 > 0.0$. A decline set in after 30 days of fumigation in the total cobalt content. The reasons for the increase and decrease

TABLE 2

CORRELATION COEFFICIENTS BETWEEN AVAILABLE COPPER, TOTAL COPPER, WATER SOLUBLE BORON, TOTAL COBALT, pH AND E.C.

Sr. No.	Form	Total Copper	Water soluble Boron	Total Cobalt	pH	E.C.
1.	Available Copper	+0.936	+0.919	+0.910	+0.528	-0.470
2.	Total Copper	—	+0.957	+0.898	+0.636	-0.361
3.	Water soluble Boron	—	—	+0.899	+0.552	-0.496
4.	Total Cobalt	—	—	—	+0.639	-0.503
5.	pH	—	—	—	—	-0.993

in total cobalt status of the soil were similar to those observed in the case of total copper. Thus the increase in total cobalt was derived from the protoplasmic constituent and vitamin B₁₂ of the dead bacteria⁶ as a result of fumigation. Then followed a re-establishment of the microorganisms after a certain period due to the gradual decay of the chemical leading to a decrease in cobalt status of the soil caused by its absorption by the bacteria.

An examination of the correlation coefficients (Table 2) revealed that water soluble boron, available copper, total copper, total cobalt and pH were all positively correlated to each other and negatively correlated to electrical conductivity pointing to an almost similar mechanism for their variations in the soil.

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